

The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions

In Southern Italy 34 out of 100 people risk poverty

Istat calculates the poverty risk defined as the "[...] percentage of people living in families with a net equivalent income below a risk-of-poverty threshold, set at 60% of the median of the individual distribution of net equivalent income. The reference year is the calendar year preceding the survey year".

Ranking of the regions by risk of poverty in 2019. Sicily, together with Campania, is in first place by value of the poverty risk with a value equal to 41%. In second place is Calabria with a risk of poverty value of 31% followed by Puglia with a risk of poverty value of 30. In the middle of the table there are Lazio with a percentage of people at risk of poverty equal to 17%, followed by Tuscany and Marche both with a value of 14% and by Piedmont and Liguria with a value of 13%. Trentino-Alto Adige and Veneto close the ranking with a value of 8.7%, followed by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 8.4 and Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 6.1%.

Percentage variation of the poverty risk between 2004 and 2019. Tuscany is in first place for percentage variation of the poverty risk between 2004 and 2019 with an amount equal to 48.96%, followed by Emilia Romagna with an amount equal to 26.74% and from Molise with an amount equal to 21.56%. In the middle of the table there are Sicily with a percentage change in the risk of poverty equal to 4.81%, followed by Piedmont with an amount equal to 4.69% and Liguria with an amount equal to 2.38%. Calabria closes the ranking with an amount equal to -13.7%, Umbria with an amount equal to -16.2% and Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 35.8%. However, substantially, if we take the average of the variations of the Italian regions by value of the risk of poverty, it appears that the risk of poverty increased by 0.9 units in the passage from 2004-2019 or by an amount equal to 5.3%.

Clusterization. Clustering is carried out below to verify if there are any groupings that can somehow reverberate the distinctions between South, Center and North Italy. This clustering was achieved using the k-Means algorithm optimized by the Silhouette coefficient and represented by the t-SNE algorithm. From the analysis carried out, the following clusters appear, namely:

- Cluster 1: Abruzzo, Sardinia and Molise;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Trentino-Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont, Marche, Umbria, Liguria;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Campania, Calabria;
- Cluster 4: Basilicata, Puglia, Molise.

As it is possible to verify, there is a cluster that contains most of the regions or cluster 2 in which there are regions of the Center-North, while the regions of the South are divided into 3 different clusters. It clearly follows that the differences between groups of regions show gradations of poverty which are particularly marked in the southern regions. From the point of view of the median it appears that the highest value is Cluster 3 with an amount of 41.20, followed by cluster 4 with an amount of the median equal to a value of 27.10, by cluster 1 with a value equal to 19.50 units and from cluster

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2 with an amount equal to 10.90 units. Specifically, the value of the poverty risk in cluster 2 is approximately 73.5% lower than the probability of poverty in the regions of cluster 3. On the other hand, among the southern regions, those with a lower risk of poverty value are contained in cluster 1, i.e. Abruzzo, Sardinia and Molise, which have a poverty risk value of approximately half the value of cluster 4.

Machine learning and predictions. Below 8 different algorithms were used to predict the value of the poverty risk through the data of the 2004-2019 period using the machine learning technique. Specifically, the following algorithms were used

- Tree Ensemble Regression;
- Simple Regression Tree;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network;
- Artificial Neural Network ANN-MLP;
- Random Forest Regression;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression;
- Linear Regression;
- Polynomial Regression.

To choose the most efficient algorithm to use, the performance of the machine learning algorithms indicated based on the following criteria was compared: "Mean Absolute Error", "Mean Squared Error", "Root Mean Squared Error", "Mean Signed Difference ". The results highlighted that the best performing algorithm is "Tree Ensemble Regression". Considering that the data were used with 70% training and 30% prediction, iterations were carried out to generate the entire set of predictions for the Italian regions. It follows that the algorithm predicted the following results, namely:

- Abruzzo: negative change in the risk of poverty from 19.50 to 19.11 or equal to a value of -0.39 units equal to -2.10%;
- Basilicata: positive change from a value of 27.10 units up to an amount of 28.51 units or equal to a value of 1.41 units equal to 5.19%;
- Calabria: positive change from a value of 30.90 units up to a value of 36.56 units or equal to an amount of 5.66 units equal to a value of 18.32%;
- Campania: negative change from an amount equal to 41.20 units up to a value equal to 33.38 units or equal to an amount of -7.82 units equal to a value of -18.97%;
- Emilia-Romagna: negative change from an amount equal to 10.90 units up to a value of 9.06 units or equal to a change of -1.84 units equal to -16.87%;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia: positive change from an amount equal to 8.40 units up to a value equal to 10.76 units or equal to an amount of 2.36 units equal to 28.07%;
- Lazio: reduction in value from an amount equal to 17.20 units up to a value equal to 16.15 units or equal to a variation of -1.05 units equal to a value of -6.09%.
- Liguria: positive change from an amount equal to 13.40 units up to a value of 13.65 units or equal to an amount of 0.25 units equal to a variation of 1.84%;
- Lombardy: negative change from an amount equal to 12.00 units up to a value of 11.40 units or equal to a change of -0.60 units equal to -5.03%;
- Marche: variation from an amount of 13.60 units up to a value of 11.46 units or equal to a variation of -2.15 units equal to -15.77%;
- Molise: variation of an amount equal to 26.50 units up to an amount of 26.58 units or equal to a variation of 0.08 units equal to an amount of 0.31%;

- Piedmont: variation from an amount of 13.40 units up to a value of 12.81 units or equal to a variation of -0.59 units equal to a value of -4.40%;
- Puglia: Variation from a value of 30.40 units up to a value of 27.50 units or equal to a value of -2.90 units equal to a value of -9.55%;
- Sardinia: variation from an amount of 22.90 units up to a value of 21.03 units or equal to a variation of -1.87 units or equal to 8.18%;
- Sicily: variation from an amount equal to 41.40 units up to a value equal to 37.28 units or equal to a value of -4.12 units equal to an amount of -9.96%;
- Tuscany: variation from an amount equal to 14.30 units up to a value of 9.97 units or equal to a variation of -4.33 units equal to a variation of -30.31%;
- Trentino-Alto Adige: change from an amount equal to 8.70 units up to a value equal to 10.77 units or equal to a change of 2.07 units equal to 23.79%;
- Umbria: change from an amount of 9.80 units up to a value of 13.32 units or equal to a change of 3.52 units equal to 35.87%;
- Valle d'Aosta: variation from an amount of 6.10 units up to a value of 11.54 units or equal to a value of 5.44 units equal to a change of 89.16%;
- Veneto: variation from an amount equal to 8.70 units up to a value of 11.33 units or equal to a variation of 2.63 units equal to an amount of 30.22%.

Overall, the average value of the poverty risk in the Italian regions is predicted by the algorithm to decrease from a value of 18.82 to a value of 18.61 units, i.e. a variation of -0.21 units equal to -1, 13%.

Conclusions. In summary, we can observe that in the southern regions the value of the risk of poverty is equal to about 2.1 times compared to the North and about 1.26 times equal to the value of the Center. Overall in percentage terms between 2004 and 2019 the value of poverty grew more in the Center with a value of + 14.18%, followed by the North + 8.74% and the South + 6.12%. However, the poverty risk values in the central regions remain very high and about 34 out of 100 people risk poverty in southern Italy, compared to 12 out of 100 in the north and 16 out of 100 in the center. However, Istat data stop at 2019 and do not allow to evaluate the impact of the citizenship income that was introduced in the same year. What can be emphasized is that the increase in the risk of poverty in Italy between 2004 and 2019 was equal to 6.35% and that obviously if this value is associated with the loss of value of the work component in GDP, together with the growing precariousness, and the presence of financial fragility, it follows that evidently a large part of the Italian population, certainly more than 20%, is at risk of poverty. To counter this phenomenon it is necessary to operate with economic policies that give greater value to work in terms of income and also through the redistribution achieved through the taxation of wealth and assets. In fact, since the Italian labor market is largely inefficient and also accompanied by low incomes even for people with school education, it follows that only a significant policy of redistribution of wealth achieved through taxation on assets can reduce the risk of poverty.

Declarations

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Appendix

	2019	Prediction	VarAss	VarPerc
Abruzzo	19,50	19,11	-0,39	-2,01
Basilicata	27,10	28,51	1,41	5,19
Calabria	30,90	36,56	5,66	18,32
Campania	41,20	33,38	-7,82	-18,97
Emilia-Romagna	10,90	9,06	-1,84	-16,87
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	8,40	10,76	2,36	28,07
Lazio	17,20	16,15	-1,05	-6,09
Liguria	13,40	13,65	0,25	1,84
Lombardia	12,00	11,40	-0,60	-5,03
Marche	13,60	11,46	-2,15	-15,77
Molise	26,50	26,58	0,08	0,31
Piemonte	13,40	12,81	-0,59	-4,40
Puglia	30,40	27,50	-2,90	-9,55
Sardegna	22,90	21,03	-1,87	-8,18
Sicilia	41,40	37,28	-4,12	-9,96
Toscana	14,30	9,97	-4,33	-30,31
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	8,70	10,77	2,07	23,79
Umbria	9,80	13,32	3,52	35,87
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	6,10	11,54	5,44	89,16
Veneto	8,70	11,33	2,63	30,22
Media	18,82	18,61	-0,21	-1,13

Ranking degli Algoritmi per Performance					
Algoritmo	Mean Absolute Error	Mean Squared Error	Root Mean Squared Error	Mean Signerd Difference	Totale
Tree Ensemble Regression	1	1	1	3	6
Simple Regressione Tree	2	2	2	1	7
PNN	3	3	3	2	11
ANN-MLP	4	4	4	4	16
Random Forest Regression	5	5	5	6	21
Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	6	6	6	5	23
Linear Regression	7	7	7	7	28
Polynomial Regression	8	8	8	8	32

Rischio Povertà nel 2019.

Variazione Rischio Povertà 2004-2019.

Risultati dell'Analisi degli Algoritmi di Machine Learning Applicati per la Predizione del Rischio di Povertà

	Mean Absolute Error	Mean Squared Error	Root Mean Squared Error	Mean Signerd Difference
ANN-MLP	0,082144562	0,009797558	0,098982613	0,045559196
PNN	0,065810328	0,008084455	0,089913596	0,008792049
Simple Regressione Tree	0,047565398	0,004365882	0,066074822	0,007239057
Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	0,117309059	0,023919168	0,154658230	0,047659106
Random Forest Regression	0,113629464	0,022200658	0,148998852	0,099764995
Tree Ensemble Regression	0,041286029	0,003124074	0,055893418	0,012975883
Linear Regression	0,469246032	0,340508078	0,583530700	0,469246032
Polynomial Regression	0,480934809	0,397752391	0,630676138	0,480934809

Variazione 2004-2019

N	Regioni	Ass	%
1	Toscana	★ 4,7	★ 48,96
2	Emilia-Romagna	★ 2,3	★ 26,74
3	Molise	★ 4,7	★ 21,56
4	Lombardia	★ 2	★ 20
5	Marche	★ 2	★ 17,24
6	Abruzzo	★ 2,7	★ 16,07
7	Campania	★ 5,6	★ 15,73
8	Sardegna	★ 2,7	★ 13,37
9	Sicilia	★ 1,9	★ 4,81
10	Piemonte	★ 0,6	★ 4,69
11	Lazio	★ 0,4	★ 2,38
12	Liguria	★ 0,1	★ 0,75
13	Puglia	★ 0	★ 0
14	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ -0,1	★ -1,14
15	Basilicata	★ -0,7	★ -2,52
16	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ -0,6	★ -6,67
17	Veneto	★ -1,1	★ -11,2
18	Calabria	★ -4,9	★ -13,7
19	Umbria	★ -1,9	★ -16,2
20	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ -3,4	★ -35,8

Valore dei Clusters

CLUSTER	Mediana	Media	Min	Max	RISPETTO C3	
C3	41,20	37,83	30,90	41,40	Ass	%
C4	27,10	28,00	26,50	30,40	-14,10	-34,22
C1	19,50	19,87	17,20	22,90	-21,70	-52,67
C2	10,90	10,90	6,10	14,30	-30,30	-73,54

	2019	TERRITORIO	Cluster
12	17.2	Lazio	C1
13	19.5	Abruzzo	C1
20	22.9	Sardegna	C1
1	13.4	Piemonte	C2
2	6.1	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2
3	13.4	Liguria	C2
4	12.0	Lombardia	C2
5	8.7	Trentino-Alto A...	C2
6	8.7	Veneto	C2
7	8.4	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2
8	10.9	Emilia-Romagna	C2
9	14.3	Toscana	C2
10	9.8	Umbria	C2
11	13.6	Marche	C2
15	41.2	Campania	C3
18	30.9	Calabria	C3
19	41.4	Sicilia	C3
14	26.5	Molise	C4
16	30.4	Puglia	C4
17	27.1	Basilicata	C4

Rischio Povertà nel 2019				
N	Regioni	2019	VarAss rispetto alla Sicilia e Campania	Var % rispetto alla Sicilia e Campania
1	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 41		
1	<i>Campania</i>	★ 41		
2	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 31	★ -10,50	★ -25,36
3	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 30	★ -11,00	★ -26,57
4	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 27	★ -14,30	★ -34,54
4	<i>Molise</i>	★ 27	★ -14,90	★ -35,99
5	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 23	★ -18,50	★ -44,69
6	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 20	★ -21,90	★ -52,90
7	<i>Lazio</i>	☆ 17	☆ -24,20	☆ -58,45
8	<i>Toscana</i>	☆ 14	☆ -27,10	☆ -65,46
8	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 14	☆ -27,80	☆ -67,15
9	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 13	☆ -28,00	☆ -67,63
9	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 13	☆ -28,00	☆ -67,63
10	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 12	☆ -29,40	☆ -71,01
11	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	☆ 11	☆ -30,50	☆ -73,67
12	<i>Umbria</i>	☆ 10	☆ -31,60	☆ -76,33
13	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	☆ 9	☆ -32,70	☆ -78,99
13	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 9	☆ -32,70	☆ -78,99
14	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 8	☆ -33,00	☆ -79,71
15	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	☆ 6	☆ -35,30	☆ -85,27

